

Self-management in action

How self-management is integrated in daily life after discharge from initial rehabilitation in individuals with a newly acquired spinal cord injury

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To those rebuilding their life from scratch. They taught me that vulnerability is not a weakness,
but a daily act of intelligence, creativity, and resolve.

This work is for you.

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Short summary

Self-management is increasingly recognized as essential to long-term health and participation following spinal cord injury (SCI). Yet dominant models often reduce self-management to a set of individual tasks, overlooking how it is shaped by everyday environments, relational dynamics, and the ongoing realities of disrupted lives. This thesis sets out to redefine what it means to self-manage after a complex chronic condition, using spinal cord injury as a condition to learn from. It develops a grounded conceptual framework of self-management in SCI, asking: How do individuals newly discharged from rehabilitation integrate and sustain SM routines within the shifting realities of their bodies, relationships, roles, and environments?

The research unfolds in two sequential phases. Phase 1 comprises two scoping reviews: the first maps trends and gaps in SCI-specific SM research; the second synthesizes qualitative findings on how self-management is sustained across chronic conditions. Phase 2 draws on a longitudinal qualitative study involving 32 participants with newly acquired SCI, producing 64 in-depth interviews at 3 and 6 months post-discharge. Across these four studies, three key insights emerged: 1) self-management is not a fixed behavior but a *situated action* of integration, shaped by bodily variability, environmental context and social dynamics; 2) people enact self-management through *bounded flexibility*, adjusting routines using strategies such as compartmentalizing, mixing, or embedding, in order to balance medical demands with everyday life; 3) self-management is fundamentally relational, dependent on *relational autonomy*—a form of agency enabled and constrained by caregivers, professionals, peers, and infrastructural support.

The implications are far-reaching. This work challenges the assumption that more knowledge or motivation is enough. It calls for interventions, technologies, and metrics that are flexible, relationally aware, and grounded in the messiness of real life. Sustainable self-management, this thesis argues, is not an individual achievement but a collective, situated process that unfolds within the entangled conditions of lived life.

List of Abbreviations

SM: Self-Management

SCI: Spinal Cord Injury

CDSMP: Stanford Chronic Disease Self-Management Program

SwiSCI: Swiss Spinal Cord Injury

ISCOS: International Spinal Cord Society

ICCH: International Conference on Communication in Healthcare

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1. Self-management

1.1. The imperative of chronic condition self-management

Chronic conditions have reached epidemic proportions, now accounting for seven of every ten deaths worldwide and consuming the majority of healthcare expenditures in high-income countries [1, 2]. Unlike acute illnesses, chronic conditions such as diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and spinal cord injury unfold over long time periods and require ongoing, multifaceted management [3]. This care extends beyond clinical encounters: individuals must monitor symptoms, adhere to complex treatment regimens, adjust daily activities, and often coordinate between multiple healthcare providers [4].

As a result, self-management (SM) has become a cornerstone in modern chronic care policy and practice [5]. SM empowers individuals to manage the medical, emotional, and social aspects of their condition [6, 7], shifting focus from clinical treatment to everyday health management [5]. Beyond patient empowerment, SM has been positioned as a strategy to reduce preventable hospitalizations, ease pressure on overstretched health systems, and foster more sustainable, cost-effective care [8]. Its promise extends beyond the individual and represents a public health opportunity to strengthen long-term care capacity, improve population-level outcomes, and align health systems more closely with the lived realities of chronic illness [9].

SM interventions, including educational programs, telehealth platforms, peer support models, and integrated care pathways [10], are now embedded into health system reforms that emphasize patient engagement and continuity of care [11]. While the specific operationalizations of SM interventions vary, and will be discussed further in the next section, all share a common premise: that improving chronic disease outcomes requires more than optimizing clinical treatment; it requires equipping individuals with the knowledge, skills, and confidence to navigate their conditions amid the complexities of everyday life [12].

1.2. Conceptual foundations of traditional self-management models

The conceptual development of SM in healthcare is rooted in cognitive behavioral psychology, particularly in the work of Albert Bandura. In the late 1970s, Bandura introduced the concept of self-efficacy as part of his broader Social Cognitive Theory [13, 14]. He argued that individuals' beliefs in their own capacity to perform specific actions (i.e., self-efficacy) are central to whether they initiate and sustain health-related behaviors [15]. This concept became foundational for early SM programs, as it provided a theoretical mechanism to explain how patients could be empowered to take more active roles in managing their conditions. Bandura identified four sources of self-efficacy: mastery experiences, vicarious learning, verbal persuasion, and interpretation of physiological states [16].

Building on this foundation, the 1990s saw the emergence of more structured, system-level approaches to SM, most notably the Chronic Care Model developed by Wagner and colleagues [17]. The Chronic Care Model reframed chronic disease care as requiring six interdependent components, one of which is SM support. Within this model, effective SM was positioned as a joint responsibility between “informed, activated patients” and “prepared, proactive healthcare teams” [18]. The emphasis shifted from education alone to collaborative care planning, problem-solving, and long-term skill-building, although still grounded in the assumption that patients would enact SM behaviors autonomously once properly trained and supported.

In parallel, Lorig and Holman developed and tested the Stanford Chronic Disease Self-Management Program (CDSMP), which became one of the most widely adopted and evaluated SM interventions [19]. The CDSMP was explicitly designed to enhance self-efficacy using peer modeling, goal setting, and action planning. They later formalized their conceptualization of SM into three domains: medical management (e.g., taking medications, managing symptoms), role management (e.g., maintaining life roles and routines), and emotional management (e.g., coping with distress, uncertainty, or frustration) [20]. They argued that effective SM education should target all three domains and should focus on skill-building rather than didactic knowledge transfer.

By the 2000s, these models were further integrated into primary care reform efforts. Bodenheimer et al. emphasized the need for SM support to be woven into routine clinical practice and highlighted self-efficacy as the mechanism of change in most SM programs [9]. Their work contributed to a broader healthcare quality movement that positioned SM as a cost-effective tool for reducing hospitalizations, improving patient satisfaction, and enhancing chronic disease outcomes [21]. A Cochrane review by Foster et al. and a later meta-analysis by Brady et al. confirmed that SM interventions, especially particularly those following the Stanford model, can improve self-efficacy, health behaviors, and quality of life, and modestly reduce healthcare utilization. However, these benefits tend to be more pronounced in the short term and often taper off over time [22, 23].

These foundational and important models share a set of core assumptions: that SM can be taught, that behavior change is the primary mechanism of health improvement, and that individuals can (and should) be activated to take personal responsibility for managing their health [6]. Most programs built on these models conceptualize SM as a set of discrete, observable behaviors that can be shaped through education, reinforcement, and goal-setting—assumptions that remain deeply embedded in contemporary health services research, policy, and practice [22]. In conditions that are particularly complex, embodied, and interdependent, such as spinal cord injury (SCI), the assumptions underpinning these models may prove difficult to operationalize, as

the realities of daily life introduce different layers of constraint and coordination that extend beyond standardized frameworks [24].

2. Spinal cord injury

2.1. Spinal cord injury as a paradigm of complex self-management

SCI represents a paradigmatic case of a complex chronic condition that disrupts nearly every domain of life [25]. With an estimated global incidence of 250,000 to 500,000 new cases annually, SCI results in varying degrees of paralysis, sensory impairment, and autonomic dysfunction, depending on the level and completeness of injury [26, 27]. Beyond immediate medical stabilization, individuals confront a relentless disease burden: constant bladder/bowel care (often evolving into chronic UTIs and renal complications), vigilant pressure ulcers prevention (risking skin ulcers), complex neuropathic pain regimens, spasticity management, and daily battles with inaccessible environments that exacerbate these secondary conditions [28, 29]. Here, SM transforms from routine healthcare into an anchor for survival and social participation [30].

In light of this thesis, SCI serves as both a clinical priority and a significant case study. Unlike single diseases, SCI forces simultaneous management of multiple interdependent secondary conditions, each with its own trajectory, each capable of triggering hospitalization [31]. By examining SM in this context, we uncover fundamental tensions in chronic care that apply across conditions, yet surface most starkly when one primary injury creates an ecosystem of chronic complications [32].

2.2. Persisting challenges in self-management of spinal cord injury

To support individuals post-injury, a range of SM interventions has been developed, spanning telehealth coaching, peer mentoring, digital platforms, and group education [33]. Programs such as *SCI Thrive* [34], *My Care My Call* [35], and nurse-led digital initiatives [36] have demonstrated improvements in occupational functioning, self-efficacy, and mitigation of depression symptoms. Growing qualitative research, however, suggests that even with targeted interventions, SCI SM remains fragile and contingent under real-world conditions [37-39]. Individuals face additional, unaddressed challenges that jeopardize the sustainability of SM practices, and that only come into surface from their lived experience.

First, SM in SCI is time-consuming, and highly vulnerable to breakdowns. Routine tasks such as catheterization, bowel management, and pressure relief must be performed with strict consistency and precision to avoid serious complications like infections, pressure ulcers, and hospitalizations [40-46]. However, maintaining this consistency is extremely

fragile. Bodily unpredictability, work demands, fatigue, and social obligations often interfere with scheduled routines, leading to skipped tasks, delayed actions, or rushed procedures [47-49]. In this way, SM is not only burdensome, but it is structurally unstable, continuously threatened by the competing pressures of daily life.

Second, SM in SCI is inherently relational, not fully under individual control. Many core responsibilities of care are distributed across caregivers, family members, and support personnel. Individuals with tetraplegia, for example, often rely on others for SM activities such as catheterization, bowel care, and mobility support [50, 51]. Even tasks like meal timing, medication intake, or repositioning are frequently structured around caregiver schedules rather than optimized medical recommendations [24, 52]. As a result, SM it is constrained by the availability, timing, and reliability of others.

Third, SM often competes with quality of life and identity preservation. After discharge from rehabilitation, individuals with SCI frequently experience a decline in social participation, emotional exhaustion, and disruptions in SM routines [53]. These patterns highlight that while initial training may equip individuals with technical skills, sustaining SM over time often collides with competing needs for autonomy, dignity, and meaningful social engagement. Adhering strictly to medical routines can come at the cost of quality of life [37].

These tensions become particularly acute during the initial post-discharge period, when individuals transition from highly structured rehabilitation settings to the unpredictable demands of everyday life [54]. It is during this transition, where institutional supports recede and personal responsibility intensifies, that SM proves most fragile [55]. And yet, this phase remains one of the least understood in both SCI research and SM frameworks more broadly [56].

2.3. The evidence gap in self-management of spinal cord injury

The aforementioned observations point to a central and unresolved problem: current models of SM assume that once taught, routines will be performed. But in practice in SCI, SM is far more complex process, one that current research has yet to fully capture or address [33, 39]. Promising research in diabetes, heart failure, and multiple sclerosis [57, 58] reframes SM as learning episodes, interruptions, and recalibrations in response to shifting bodily conditions and life demands [59]. These studies highlight SM as deeply contextual, requiring emotional interpretation, social negotiation, and meaning-making, rather than mere instruction-following [60, 61].

Yet in SCI, critical questions remain unanswered: How do individuals integrate SM into their post-rehabilitation lives? When and why do routines succeed or collapse? For instance, bowel management routines, often requiring 1–2 hours daily, frequently conflict with work

schedules or caregiving responsibilities, forcing impossible trade-offs [38]. We still lack data on how SM practices emerge, adapt, or wear away over time, and the contextual factors that sustain them [38, 39]. This evidence gap has direct consequences: individuals with SCI face elevated health risks after discharge, with short-term readmission rates remaining alarmingly high [62]. A recent meta-analysis found that 14.2% of patients are readmitted within 30 days, rising to 35.7% within 90 days, with infections, pressure injuries, and secondary complications as leading causes, many of which may be preventable with adequate SM support [63]. Failing to understand what happens after discharge means missing the opportunity to support people precisely when their SM is most vulnerable and most consequential.

3. The doctoral thesis

This thesis aims to develop a new, grounded, conceptual framework for understanding SM in SCI — one that captures how SM is actually sustained, recalibrated, or disrupted after initial rehabilitation. Concretely, it asks: **How do individuals newly discharged from rehabilitation negotiate SM within the shifting realities of their bodies, relationships, roles, and environments?** In asking this question, the thesis seeks to challenge prevailing behaviorist paradigms and contribute **a patient-centered theory of SM as lived negotiation.**

To advance this aim, the research unfolds in two sequential phases (see Figure 1), each designed to clarify our research question. Phase 1 lays the conceptual groundwork by synthesizing existing SM literature in SCI and across chronic conditions. This phase concretely pursued two objectives: 1) To map trends in SCI-specific SM research, with a focus on study designs, theoretical underpinnings, and methodological limitations. The goal was to identify persistent conceptual blind spots and empirical gaps, especially in relation to sustainability and daily-life SM integration; and 2) To examine how the integration of SM into everyday life is experienced across chronic conditions. The goal was to highlight common pattern, tensions and contextual dynamics that might inform a broader theory of SM beyond SCI. Phase 2 builds on these insights by empirically investigating how individuals with newly acquired SCI navigate SM in the early post-discharge period. This phase concretely focused on 3) Exploring how individuals initiate and adapt SM routines within the first 3 months after discharge. The goal was to identify distinct integration approaches and the early tensions that shape these patterns; and 4) Investigating how SM-related decisions evolve over time, up to 6 months post-discharge. The goal was to understand how priorities, capacities, and support systems shape the sustainability and adaptability of SM.

Across both phases, the research aims to move beyond documenting behaviors and their barriers. Instead, it seeks to develop a conceptual framework that reflects the **real-life**

dynamics of embedding, adjusting, and co-managing SM in unpredictable, relationally dense, and resource-constrained settings.

Figure 1: Sequential design of the thesis

3.1. Thesis contribution

This thesis makes significant contributions to SCI SM research through theoretical, methodological, and societal advancements. *Theoretically*, it challenges dominant paradigms by reconceptualizing SM as the lived work of integrating health practices into daily life's complexity. Grounded in participant narratives, the framework introduces three key innovations: *situated action*, which recognizes SM as context-dependent adaptation; *bounded flexibility*, describing routines that adapt within constraints without breaking; and *relational autonomy*, highlighting how agency emerges through social and technological supports.

Methodologically, the study advances qualitative health research through its longitudinal design, tracking individuals with new SCI during the precarious post-rehabilitation transition. By applying reflexive thematic analysis across two critical time points, it reveals not just what people do to manage their health, but how and why their practices evolve, or collapse, under shifting bodily conditions, social dynamics, and environmental barriers.

Societally, the findings call for a recalibration of health interventions, clinical education, and policy frameworks, that moves away from assumptions of autonomous compliance and toward models that support shared, adaptive, and socially embedded practices of care [64]. This

has direct implications for public health, particularly in understanding how chronic care is negotiated outside institutional settings, how preventable strain on health systems can be mitigated, and how structural, technological and relational conditions shape long-term health outcomes [65, 66].

Together, these contributions bridge the critical gap between institutional care protocols and the realities of living with SCI, while offering a roadmap for more equitable, prevention-oriented chronic care systems.

3.2. Methodological framework

Throughout the thesis, integration was approached not as a binary outcome, but as a practical question: whether and how SM routines become embedded in the flow of everyday life. In the first phase, particularly during the scoping review of chronic conditions, this was understood through reported challenges to sustaining routines, applying knowledge flexibly, or coordinating SM tasks with daily roles and responsibilities. This operationalization was shaped by qualitative literature in the field [57, 60, 61] that highlight SM as a situated, adaptive process. While the concept of integration was refined over the course of the empirical studies, these initial insights informed both the analytic lens and the development of the interview guide.

3.2.1. Conceptual orientation of the scoping reviews

The two reviews followed established scoping methodologies, including the Arksey and O'Malley framework and PRISMA-ScR reporting guidelines, and were designed to map conceptual and empirical developments in the field [67-69]. The first review, focused on SCI-specific SM literature, employed both *descriptive mapping* and *thematic synthesis* to identify research trends, conceptual gaps, and dominant framings of SM in SCI. The second review, exploring SM integration across chronic conditions, relied on *narrative thematic analysis* of qualitative findings to identify recurring challenges in sustaining SM in daily life. This review was particularly influenced by interpretivist and realist traditions, emphasizing how SM is enacted (or disrupted) within environmental, interpersonal, and structural contexts [70, 71]. Both reviews helped define the conceptual terrain on which the empirical studies were built.

3.2.2. Epistemological and ontological positioning of the empirical studies

The empirical component of the thesis is grounded in an interpretivist epistemology and a critical realist ontology [70, 71]. This combination reflects the thesis's commitment to understanding SM not simply as a set of discrete behaviors, but as a situated, meaning-laden process shaped by both subjective interpretations and real-world constraints. From an

interpretivist standpoint, the empirical work seeks to uncover how individuals with SCI make sense of SM as they return to life outside institutional settings. It assumes that knowledge about SM integration is co-produced through participants' narratives and the researcher's interpretive engagement with those narratives. Rather than measuring pre-defined constructs like adherence or efficacy, the studies explore participants' own understandings, decisions, and adjustments as they navigate complex bodily, social, and environmental realities. This epistemological stance is anchored in a critical realist ontology, which acknowledges that individuals' experiences are shaped by tangible material structures, such as bodily impairment, caregiver availability, and environmental accessibility, but that these structures must be interpreted through personal, cultural, and relational lenses [70]. SM is understood here as neither purely personal nor entirely constrained; it is enacted through decisions, adaptations, and negotiations in context.

3.2.3. Analytic approach of the empirical studies

Both empirical studies employed reflexive thematic analysis as outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006, 2019), with an inductive, experiential orientation. The analysis allowed codes and themes to emerge iteratively from participants' accounts. Attention was paid to how participants described the evolution of routines, the tensions they encountered in relation to other life activities, and the strategies they adopted or abandoned. Reflexivity was central to the analytic process. The research team maintained reflective field notes and memos throughout data collection and analysis, explicitly considering how their own assumptions, positions, and backgrounds might shape data interpretation. This approach ensured that findings were not treated as objective representations, but as co-constructed understandings of SM in everyday life.

3.3. Individual studies

3.3.1. Study 1: Trends and gaps in SCI self-management research

This scoping review identified persistent conceptual blind spots and empirical gaps, especially in relation to sustainability and daily-life SM integration. A total of 2,792 abstracts were screened, with 92 full texts assessed for eligibility. Ultimately, 52 studies were included for synthesis, encompassing data from 2,260 individuals across studies. By identifying where and how SM research has the tendency to focus (particularly its emphasis on education and behavior change), it revealed a critical lack of attention to lived, contextualized experiences of SM. This validated the need for a deeper, qualitative inquiry into SM integration as a process shaped by daily life, not just clinical goals.

3.3.2. Study 2: Challenges of integrating self-management in chronic conditions

Conducted in parallel, this scoping review examined qualitative studies of SM across a range of chronic conditions, focusing specifically on how individuals manage SM within the context of everyday life. The aim was to help operationalizing SM “integration”, for the empirical upcoming studies. This review included 22 qualitative or mixed-methods studies, selected from an initial pool of 9,360 abstracts and 717 full texts. These represented data from over 690 participants. The studies focused on SM performance in everyday environments across a range of chronic conditions, including diabetes, cardiovascular disease, lung disease, rheumatic conditions, kidney disease, and spinal cord injury. The synthesis revealed recurring obstacles to integration, including environmental limitations, informational gaps, and social dynamics; findings that informed the design of the empirical interview guides.

3.3.3. Study 3: Approaches to self-management integration post-discharge (3 Months)

The first empirical study explored how individuals with newly acquired SCI begin integrating SM into their daily routines after discharge from inpatient rehabilitation. The aim was to identify the range of approaches people take and to understand the factors influencing these strategies. By focusing on early adaptation, this study provided a descriptive foundation of SM integration as a negotiated, context-sensitive process, moving through three different approaches: compartmentalizing, where health and life tasks were kept separate and prioritized sequentially; mixing, where individuals adjusted routines and made trade-offs to balance competing demands; and embedding, where SM practices were seamlessly incorporated into everyday activities through planning, habit formation, or support.

3.3.4. Study 4: Decision-making in self-management (3–6 Months)

This second empirical study built directly on the prior one by examining how SM decision-making evolves over the first six months after discharge. By re-interviewing participants at two timepoints, the study captured not only the decisions made, but the reasoning behind them, and how that reasoning changed. This iterative design, where the second interview was informed by the first, enabled a deeper exploration of decision trajectories, shifts in priorities, and the contextual pressures influencing each decision. The study identified five distinct decision-making styles (delayed, collaborative, reflexive, impulsive, and strategic), each reflecting a different way of navigating the demands of SM. These styles were not fixed traits but dynamic responses to bodily, environmental and social influences.

3.4. *The umbrella project*

This doctoral thesis is part of a larger project funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation that explores the existential dimension of SM in chronic conditions, using SCI as a case in point. The broader project follows individuals with newly acquired SCI over the course of 18 months after discharge from initial rehabilitation, using longitudinal qualitative methods to capture how SM unfolds and evolves over time. In particular, the project collects serial in-depth interviews at approximately three, six, twelve, and eighteen months post-discharge. The studies included in this thesis draw on data collected within this larger framework, specifically focusing on the three- and six-month time points. Data were collected through the Swiss Spinal Cord Injury (SwiSCI) cohort study, within Pathway 3, which tracks the transition from rehabilitation to community life in Switzerland [72]. Study 1 involved 32 participants interviewed once, three months after discharge from inpatient rehabilitation. A total of 32 semi-structured interviews were conducted between November 2022 and May 2024, each lasting 21 to 82 minutes. Participants were recruited from four rehabilitation centers across Switzerland and varied in age, gender, and injury characteristics (including both complete and incomplete injuries and varying levels of paraplegia and tetraplegia). Study 2 followed the same 32 participants over two time points, three and six months post-discharge, resulting in a total of 64 interviews conducted between November 2022 and August 2024. This dataset offers a longitudinal window into the early development and adjustment of SM practices and decision-making during the critical post-discharge period.

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Chapter 2

Trends in self-management research in spinal cord injury: A scoping review of study designs and findings

Qama E., Rubinelli S., & Diviani N. (submitted on 20.06.2024, in second revision process). Trends in self-management research in spinal cord injury: A scoping review of study designs and findings. *Journal of Spinal Cord Medicine*

Chapter 3

Factors influencing the integration of self-management in daily life routines in chronic conditions: a scoping review of qualitative evidence

Qama, E., Rubinelli, S., & Diviani, N. (2022). Factors influencing the integration of self-management in daily life routines in chronic conditions: a scoping review of qualitative evidence. *BMJ open*, 12(12), e066647. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2022-066647>

Chapter 4

Approaches to self-management integration and influencing factors in everyday life after spinal cord injury: A qualitative narrative analysis

Qama, E., Diviani, N., Häfliger, C., Jordan, X., Scheel-Sailer, A., Zanini, C., & Rubinelli, S. (2025). Approaches to self-management integration and influencing factors in everyday life after spinal cord injury: A qualitative narrative analysis. *Patient education and counseling*, 136, 108763. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2025.108763>

Chapter 5

Self-management decision-making in spinal cord injury after initial rehabilitation: A thematic narrative analysis

Qama, E., Diviani, N., Häfliger, C., Jordan, X., Scheel-Sailer, A., Zanini, C., & Rubinelli, S. (submitted on 17.03.2025, in revision process). Self-management decision-making in spinal cord injury after initial rehabilitation: A thematic narrative analysis. *Patient Education and Counseling*

Chapter 6

Discussion and conclusion

1. Interpretation of findings

1.1. General overview

This thesis reframes SM in SCI by grounding it in the realities of post-injury life, where clinical routines adapt to unpredictable bodies, competing responsibilities, and fragile support systems. Through four sequential studies, it moves beyond documenting the challenges of SM to reveal how individuals sustain health practices despite them. Its findings are organized into three core insights, each of which directly addresses the challenges in the field and conceptual gaps identified in the introduction chapter.

The first insight (Section 1.2) critiques the persistent reductionism of current SM models, which overemphasize discrete behaviors and individual responsibility while underestimating the structural, emotional, and logistical frictions people face in daily life. It sets the stage for a rethinking of SM not as static adherence, but as a process of integration.

The second insight (Section 1.3), explains SM integration by how people adjust, delay, or reconfigure health routines using flexible approaches, what we term compartmentalizing, mixing, and embedding. These adjustments emerge from *situated action*, where decisions are made amid real-life pressures such as time constraints, emotional strain, or the need for validation. Rather than seeing flexibility as non-adherence, this thesis proposes the concept of *bounded flexibility* to capture how individuals adapt SM routines within personal, relational, and environmental limits.

The third insight (Section 1.4) deepens this by illustrating how SM integration and its sustainability are not individual achievements, but outcomes of an infrastructures involving caregivers, peers, and health professionals. These networks of support do more than assist; they co-construct what SM is possible in the first place. In this light, the thesis advances the idea of *relational autonomy*, redefining autonomy as the capacity to act through mutual recognition, responsiveness, and co-decision-making.

This thesis traces these patterns across early post-rehabilitation period. It exposes the underlying efforts of making SM work when institutional structures fade, offering a more nuanced understanding of what sustainability requires. This perspective, in this time period, bridges the gap between knowing what to do (learned in rehab setting), and being able to do it (implementation outside the rehab).

1.2. Refining the focus of self-management research

Across both scoping reviews, this thesis highlights that, while the field has evolved in terms of study design and intervention types, core conceptual and practical blind spots remain.

These include the fragmentation of SM activities from daily life, an overemphasis on task adherence, and a tendency to prioritize institutional priorities over patients' lived needs.

Study 1 shows that medical routines remain the central unit of analysis in SM research. Interventions focus mostly on medical routines such as pressure relief or bladder care, targeting frequency or correctness as main outcomes. Yet whether these practices are sustainable, meaningful, or feasible over time remains almost entirely unexplored. Even as more studies have begun to include feasibility and qualitative designs, few question whether these behaviors are meaningful or livable. The review also points to a disconnect between what matters to institutions and what matters to individuals. For instance, many interventions address clinical indicators of concern to professionals, but neglect goals tied to personal meaning, identity, or participation, factors known to shape adherence and motivation [1].

This pattern is not surprising. As literature on the institutional framing of SM has noted, there is a persistent tendency to conceptualize SM as a technical task requiring behavioral correction, rather than as a socially situated practice shaped by relational dynamics, systemic constraints, and lived complexity [2]. Self-care interventions and tools often reflect organizational logics of control and optimization, leaving little room for improvisation, negotiation, or patient-led adaptation [3].

The tendency to approach SM as a technical problem requiring behavioral correction is further reflected in the types of knowledge prioritized, as seen in Study 2. Most interventions deliver educational content about risk factors and preventive strategies, with less emphasis on how individuals interpret bodily signals, navigate conflicting demands, or improvise care under non-ideal conditions. Integration into daily life, for instance, is noted as a topic in some studies in both reviews, yet rarely examined in depth.

1.3. *Understanding self-management as situated integration*

Building on the limitations identified in current SM literature, this thesis offers an alternative perspective derived from our empirical findings: SM is not a fixed set of routines, but as a dynamic process of integration, what this thesis terms *situated action* (Figure 2). Participants across both empirical studies, described SM as unstable, not fully routinized, but continually recalibrated based on bodily states, social expectations, and environmental context.

Study 3 introduces three typologies of integration approaches—compartmentalizing, mixing, and embedding, each reflecting how individuals manage the tensions between health demands and everyday life. These approaches emerged as context-responsive tactics, neither stable personality traits nor fixed stages of development. Their use often transcended the binary of adherence and nonadherence. One participant, for example, followed their catheterization schedule with full consistency, embedding it into their driving routines. Another practiced

pressure relief reliably, but applied a mixing approach, delaying it during social engagements and compensating later in private. These patterns illustrate what we term *bounded flexibility*: a form of adaptive SM in which practices are neither rigidly executed nor spontaneously abandoned, but flexibly adjusted to preserve both health and livability.

Study 4 reinforces this view through a lens of decision-making styles. Participants alternated between strategic, impulsive, reflexive, and collaborative modes, depending on what the situation demanded. The same individual might show strategic control in managing medications, yet delay responding to new symptoms when overwhelmed, revealing reasoning as situational, not fixed.

Other strands of chronic illness literature likewise challenge the assumption that SM unfolds as a linear process of adherence. Instead, they consistently portray it as a situated, evolving negotiation, shaped less by clinical timelines and more by the competing demands of daily life [4, 5]. Across conditions like diabetes, heart failure, and chronic pain, research has shown that individuals often recalibrate routines to preserve quality of life, manage emotional burdens, and maintain social roles [6, 7].

To interpret these findings, Normalization Process Theory offers a useful lens [8]. Its four components—coherence, cognitive participation, collective action, and reflexive monitoring—are reflected in participants' experiences. Participants engaged in meaning-making (e.g., “figuring out what really matters”), recruited social input when needed (collaboration), enacted practices under constraint (modification, skipping, combining), and reflected on whether they were “doing enough” or “doing it right.” These processes all unfold within the intimate spaces of home, relationships, and self-understanding through personal lived experience.

Figure 2. The situated compass of SM integration

1.4. The relational infrastructure of self-management

SM is commonly conceptualized as the responsibility of an autonomous individual. Someone who, once equipped with knowledge and motivation, can independently carry out health-related routines. Yet across the studies in this thesis, the data reveal SM as a relational process, one grounded in the everyday availability of caregivers, the guidance of health professionals, and the affirming presence of peers. In this view, relationality appears as a condition of possibility for SM.

Study 4 offers clear evidence for this through the lens of decision-making styles. Participants described delaying certain SM activities not from neglect but because key caregivers were unavailable. Others relied on physiotherapists or family members to validate and co-shape decisions. Collaborative decision-making emerged as a way to compensate for uncertainty, distribute risk, and share responsibility.

This pattern of relational dependence is echoed in Study 2. Participants across chronic conditions described a persistent mismatch between clinical instruction and everyday execution. Even when individuals knew what to do, they often lacked the material or relational scaffolding to act. Rigid protocols collapsed under emotional fatigue, logistical obstacles, or the moral

pressures of caregiving. Women in particular, described deprioritizing their own health due to role expectations and household responsibilities not as a failure of motivation, but as a reflection of competing social obligations.

These findings suggest that the widely discussed “intention–action gap” in SM may be better understood as a relational misalignment. SM falters not due to ignorance or indifference, but because the social infrastructures necessary to sustain it, such as, transport, care partners, and emotional support are absent. What appears as “nonadherence” may often reflect systemic failures to support shared health work.

And yet, as Study 1 demonstrates, SCI research continues to treat relationality as peripheral. Few studies explicitly examine how care networks coordinate around SM tasks, even though the management of tetraplegia makes solo responsibility logistically impossible [9]. This blind spot coexists with growing evidence of caregiver burden, suggesting a troubling contradiction: we expect individuals to “self”-manage while neglecting the relational infrastructures that make SM feasible [10].

These findings align with broader calls in disability studies and care ethics to redefine autonomy, not as independence, but as *relational autonomy* [11, 12]. From this perspective, autonomy is not compromised by relying on others; it is enacted through responsiveness, mutual recognition, and co-decision-making.

2. Implications for research and practice

SM research has long prioritized behavior performance, adherence, and knowledge acquisition as primary outcomes. Yet the findings in this thesis suggest that sustainability in SM is not captured by task completion alone, but by how well practices are sustained amid shifting bodily conditions, social responsibilities, and environmental context. The evidence calls for a fundamental shift: from measuring compliance to assessing contextual fit; from documenting isolated behaviors to tracing adaptation over time; and from viewing SM as an individual endeavor to understanding it as a distributed practice embedded in relationships and infrastructures (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Conceptual shift from behavior change to contextual integration in self-management

Traditional SM assumptions	Reframed assumptions (This thesis)
SM is a situated evolving practice	
Integration into daily life is the key to sustainability	
Breakdown often signals contextual or structural constraints	
SM is relational, co-managed, and dependent on others	
Effective SM must be negotiated and adapted in context	
Long-term integration often diverges from short-term outcomes	

2.1. Rethinking the research paradigm

To advance the shift this thesis advocates for, future research must move beyond narrow behaviorist frameworks. The typologies developed in this thesis offer a starting point: tracking integration approaches (compartmentalizing, mixing, embedding) and decision-making styles (strategic, reflexive, impulsive, collaborative, delayed) allows for more nuanced, ecologically valid representations of SM. Instead of asking whether patients perform health behaviors, researchers can investigate how those behaviors are adapted, negotiated, or deprioritized in everyday life.

This reframing also demands a reconsideration of research timelines. Longitudinal designs can capture the evolution of SM strategies as people age, take on new roles, or lose support systems [13].

2.2. Clinical and rehabilitation implications

For clinicians and rehabilitation teams, this perspective shifts the center of gravity from protocol adherence to sustainable integration. It is no longer sufficient to ask whether a patient catheterizes; we must ask how they do so, amid fatigue, caregiving duties, or emotionally

demanding days [14]. The same participant who manages medications with color-coded precision might delay bladder checks when having work, not from negligence, but due to real-time triaging of competing needs.

Supporting SM, then, means identifying decision-making styles and working with them. Offering anticipatory planning tools for strategic patients, building relational trust for those prone to delay, or strengthening collaborative scaffolds for those navigating health through networks of care. Rehabilitation encounters should transition from static education to dynamic troubleshooting, to help patients test and revise routines in contexts that matter to them [15].

2.3. Designing for relational and contextual fit

As this thesis shows, SM unfolds not in isolation but through relational scaffolding. Education and planning must engage the people who make health routines feasible in daily life, whether through transport, encouragement, or emotional anchoring. Similarly, SM technologies, like apps, reminders, trackers, should prioritize features that allow rescheduling, restructuring, or skipping tasks without penalty [16]. Recent digital health platforms have already begun moving in this direction, incorporating shared calendars, caregiver-linked dashboards, and adaptive prompts that respond to users' evolving needs [17, 18]. Others have explored how individuals engage with SM technologies not just to execute tasks, but to preserve autonomy through future-oriented planning and socially embedded routines [19].

Narrative decision-tracking tools, for instance, could support reflection not only on what was done, but why a particular course of action made sense at that time. Visual dashboards showing time or energy trade-offs, (like some prototypes for multimorbidity support [20]), could help users anticipate overload, prioritize actions, and synchronize health tasks with the broader rhythms of life. In all cases, the aim is not just to improve adherence, but to design with the logic of lived flexibility in mind.

2.4. Building adaptive systems and policies

What this thesis emphasizes is that SM support cannot be built on static checklists or linear scripts. Engaging individuals with SCI and their support networks in the co-design of health interventions ensures that these programs are relevant and sustainable. Community-Based Participatory Research frameworks have been effectively utilized to involve individuals with SCI as active partners in developing, implementing, and evaluating interventions aimed at improving health outcomes [21]. For instance, the PHOENIX program, a peer-supported, community-engaged SCI SM intervention, demonstrates the feasibility and benefits of such collaborative approaches [22].

Policy and evaluation systems must follow suit. Reimbursement models should recognize caregiver training, peer-support access, and network resilience. Recent policy developments have introduced reimbursement opportunities for caregiver training, acknowledging the critical role caregivers play in patient rehabilitation. The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services have approved new codes that allow for the reimbursement of caregiver training services, emphasizing the importance of equipping caregivers with the necessary skills to support patient care effectively [23].

Finally, clinics could pilot "living guidelines", that are protocols updated by clinician-patient communities to reflect context-sensitive adaptations. The concept of "living guidelines" involves the continuous updating of clinical protocols based on real-time feedback from both clinicians and patients [24]. Co-design methodologies have been identified as enabling factors in developing patient-centered healthcare services, facilitating the creation of adaptable and responsive care protocols that reflect the evolving needs of patients [25].

2.5. Sustaining knowledge translation through everyday adaptation

While health systems increasingly focus on translating evidence into practice, this thesis suggests that the final frontier of knowledge translation is not the institution, but the everyday lives of those expected to enact their own care. Clinical guidelines and interventions may be adapted to local contexts, but for people living with SCI, translation is a daily task. These findings echo critiques from chronic illness literature, which warn against rigid, top-down implementation models that neglect real-world fluctuations [26, 27]. But this thesis extends that critique, suggesting that translation is not a hand-off from science to patient. Knowledge must remain alive across changing circumstances, held not only by professionals but also by caregivers, peers, and technologies capable of evolving with the user [28, 29]. In this light, knowledge translation becomes a shared endeavor, that requires tools, systems, and policies that support responsive adaptation.

3. Transferability beyond spinal cord injury

Although rooted in the specific context of SCI, the findings of this thesis speak to broader dynamics of SM across chronic conditions. In SCI, the work of SM is unusually visible: routines are non-negotiable, demands are complex, and its consequences immediate [30]. This intensity acts as a magnifying lens, revealing patterns such as, the need for bounded flexibility, the role of relational scaffolding, and the friction between medical plans and lived routines, that also exist in other conditions. In this sense, SCI serves as a clarifying case [31].

Comparable dynamics have been documented in diabetes, heart failure, and chronic pain, where patients constantly adapt, delay, or negotiate health routines amid competing priorities

[16, 32, 33]. What differs is not the presence of these challenges, but their visibility and expression across contexts [34]. The conceptual frameworks developed in this thesis, such as integration strategies, decision-making styles, and relational infrastructures, can thus offer a transferable lens for studying and supporting SM in other conditions. Naturally, applying them elsewhere, requires sensitivity to condition-specific demands, care structures, and sociocultural norms. But the underlying insight, that SM is never just a matter of individual discipline, but a relational, situated, and adaptive process across conditions, holds the same.

4. Strengths and limitations

This thesis offers several key strengths. First and foremost, to our best knowledge, this work is the first of its kind (conceptually and methodologically) in the field of rehabilitation and self-management in SCI. Conceptually, its strength lies in theorizing SM not as a set of behaviors, but as an adaptive, relational, and situated process grounded in real-life constraints. Methodologically, by combining two scoping reviews with two rounds of sequential qualitative interviews, the thesis was able to both map the conceptual terrain and examine lived experience in depth and time. The empirical studies employed reflexive thematic analysis with an experiential and interpretive orientation, allowing themes to emerge inductively from participant accounts rather than being imposed a priori. The trustworthiness of the qualitative work was reinforced through several strategies. First, prolonged engagement was achieved by following participants across two interview points, allowing the study to capture evolving experiences and emergent decision-making patterns. Moreover, the analytic process was collaborative and reflexive, with findings regularly discussed within an interdisciplinary research team and shaped through team coding and audit trail documentation.

Secondly, the work presented in this thesis was developed through continuous collaboration with an interdisciplinary team that included clinicians, social scientists, rehabilitation specialists, and health communication experts. The integration of perspectives shaped both the formulation of research questions and the interpretation of findings, allowing the analysis to remain grounded in the complexity of real-world practice while advancing conceptual clarity. In addition, findings were presented and discussed in international academic forums — including the International Spinal Cord Society (ISCOS) and the International Conference on Communication in Healthcare (ICCH) — where peer feedback further refined the analytical focus and expanded its relevance across disciplinary and cultural boundaries.

At the same time, several limitations should be acknowledged. Although the sample of participants was diverse in terms of injury characteristics, all empirical work was conducted in the context of the Swiss rehabilitation system. The Swiss System is a relatively high-resource setting characterized by structured follow-up care, access to social support services, and strong

patient-provider communication norms [35]. As a result, the findings may not fully reflect the challenges experienced in lower-resource or structurally marginalized contexts. Additionally, while the scoping reviews provided an important conceptual foundation, their reliance on published literature may underrepresent unpublished practices, informal knowledge systems, or emerging interventions not captured in traditional academic outlets. This limitation is especially relevant in the context of digital and peer-led SM supports, which are often documented in grey literature or informal networks. Despite these limitations, the thesis offers a novel and grounded conceptual framework of SM post-rehabilitation, one that is attentive to lived complexity and offers both critique and constructive direction for future research, practice, and design.

5. Conclusions

This thesis makes an original contribution to SM research in SCI by advancing theoretical, methodological, and societal understanding of how health practices are enacted after rehabilitation. It challenges dominant paradigms that equate SM with individual responsibility and behavioral adherence. Instead, it offers a new conceptual framework grounded in patient experience, one that sees SM not as a checklist of actions, but as a dynamic, situated process shaped by bodily variability, environmental context, and social dynamics. The framework is built around three key conceptual anchors: *situated action*, recognizing SM as real-time adjustment to unfolding contexts; *bounded flexibility*, capturing how individuals modify routines within livable limits; and *relational autonomy*, which redefines agency as something sustained through mutual responsiveness and shared decision-making.

These insights expose critical blind spots in current SM systems. Traditional behaviorist frameworks focus on isolated behaviors, individual effort, and one-time outcomes. They rarely account for the fluid, relational, and iterative nature of real-world SM. Similarly, many interventions and technologies are designed for users imagined as self-contained actors, rather than as people embedded in shifting networks of support. This thesis therefore calls for a shift across research, practice, and policy; from measuring adherence to understanding contextual fit; from static interventions to adaptive infrastructures.

What become apparent is a vision of SM support rooted in truth rather than idealization. People do not sustain SM because they are perfectly disciplined, but because they make it livable. Systems that fail to honor this will continue to be challenged under their own constructs. The task ahead is not to fix people's behaviors, but to build clinical, technological, and social systems that are strong enough to support the complexity of SM. That is not just a research imperative. It is an ethical one.

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Supplementary material

List of scientific publications

Publications related to PhD thesis	Status (submitted, accepted, published)
First author	
Qama E., Rubinelli S., & Diviani N. Trends in self-management research in spinal cord injury: A scoping review of study designs and findings. <i>Journal of Spinal Cord Medicine</i>	Submitted on 20.06.2024 <i>Journal of Spinal Cord Medicine</i> , in second revision process
Qama, E., Rubinelli, S., & Diviani, N. (2022). Factors influencing the integration of self-management in daily life routines in chronic conditions: a scoping review of qualitative evidence. <i>BMJ open</i> , 12(12), e066647. https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2022-066647	Published
Qama, E., Diviani, N., Häfliger, C., Jordan, X., Scheel-Sailer, A., Zanini, C., & Rubinelli, S. (2025). Approaches to self-management integration and influencing factors in everyday life after spinal cord injury: A qualitative narrative analysis. <i>Patient education and counseling</i> , 136, 108763. Advance online publication. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2025.108763	Published
Qama, E., Diviani, N., Häfliger, C., Jordan, X., Scheel-Sailer, A., Zanini, C., & Rubinelli, S. Self-management decision-making in spinal cord injury after initial rehabilitation: A thematic narrative analysis. <i>Patient Education and Counseling</i>	Submitted on 17.03.2025 <i>Patient Education and Counseling</i> , in revision process
Co-author author	
Diviani, N., Qama, E., Brach, M., Gemperli, A., Jordan, X., Scheel-Sailer, A., & Rubinelli, S. (2024). The Complexity of Health Self-Management Behavior. Beliefs and Attitudes of Individuals Living With Spinal Cord Injury in Switzerland. <i>American journal of physical medicine & rehabilitation</i> , 103(11S Suppl 3), S295–S302. https://doi.org/10.1097/PHM.0000000000002532	Published
Publications non related to PhD thesis	
Qama, E., Velić, S., Diviani, N., & Rubinelli, S. (2023). Patients' perception of hope in palliative care: A systematic review and narrative synthesis. <i>Patient education and counseling</i> , 115, 107879. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2023.107879	Published
Qama, E., Diviani, N., Grignoli, N., & Rubinelli, S. (2022). Health professionals' view on the role of hope and communication challenges with patients in palliative care: A systematic narrative review. <i>Patient education and counseling</i> , 105(6), 1470–1487. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2021.09.025	Published

Conferences and presentations

Presentations / Posters	Location	Date
Presentation: PhD study	SPF Colloquium	17.11.2021; 22.02.2022
Presentation: PhD project	PhD Colloquium	23.09.2020; 17.11.2021; 06.12.2024
Poster: PhD study	ISCoS (International Spinal Cord Society Annual Scientific Meeting)	10.10.2023
Presentation: PhD study Poster: PhD study	ICCH (International Conference of Communication in Healthcare)	08.09.2022; 12.09.2024
Presentation: PhD studies	DMGP (Deutschsprachigen Medizinischen Gesellschaft für Paraplegiologie)	19.04.2023
Poster: PhD Project	Scientific Advisory Board Meeting Nottwil – Switzerland, online	17.06.2021; 21.11. 2023